

1 Annotated Sequence Record
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7 **Complete nucleotide sequence of a new variant of Grapevine rupestris stem**
8 **pitting-associated virus from southern Italy**
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1 Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus (GRSPaV), genus *Foveavirus*, family
2 *Betaflexiviridae*, is one of the most common viruses of grapevine, widely distributed in many,
3 if not all, grape-growing areas of the world. This virus is thought to be involved in the
4 ‘Rugose wood’ complex (RW) as the putative agent of the disorder known as Rupestris stem
5 pitting (RSP) [1], and some of its strains were shown to have a very close association with
6 Vein necrosis disease (VN) [2, 3]. This virus is also associated with Syrah decline [4] and its
7 possible involvement in other disorders was also suggested [5, 6].
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10 Following GRSPaV characterization at the end of the 1990’s [1, 7] a number of
11 studies have disclosed the remarkable genetic variability of the virus, which may reflect on
12 the puzzling pattern of its biological effects. Molecular investigations have led to complete
13 sequencing of six viral isolates named GRSPaV-1 (accession no. AF057136), GRSPV
14 (AF026278), GRSPaV-SG1 (AY881626), GRSPaV-BS (AY881627), GRSPaV-SY
15 (AY368590) and GRSPaV-PN (AY368172).
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18 We now report the complete nucleotide (nt) sequence of a new viral isolate (GRSPaV-
19 MG), deposited in GenBank under the accession number FR691076.
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22 **Virus source and sequencing strategy**

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30 The source plant of GRSPaV-MG was an accession of *Vitis vinifera* cv. Moscato
31 giallo (MG) from Apulia (southern Italy), from a collection of grapevine germplasm of the
32 University of Bari, established in the framework of a regional clonal selection programme. In
33 accordance with the selection protocol, the grape accession in question underwent laboratory
34 analysis (ELISA and PCR) for the presence of major grapevine viruses, i.e. Grapevine fanleaf
35 virus (GFLV), Arabis mosaic virus (ArMV), Grapevine leafroll-associated virus 1, 2, 3 and 7
36 (GLRaV-1, -2, -3 and -7), Grapevine virus A (GVA), Grapevine virus B (GVB) and
37 Grapevine fleck virus (GFkV), and indexing in the field with the following indicators: *V.*
38 *rupestris*, *V. riparia*, LN33, 110 Richter, Kober 5BB and *V. vinifera* cv. Cabernet franc.
39 Laboratory tests were consistently negative for all the above viruses, and no reaction was
40 shown by indicators, except for 110 Richter, which responded with VN symptoms. The same
41 symptoms were also shown 21 days post inoculation by glasshouse-grown green-grafted 6-
42 month-old 110R plants. GRSPaV presence in the MG accession and in symptomatic 110R
43 was confirmed by Western blot and RT-PCR.
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1 Total RNAs were silica-extracted [8] from dormant cane scrapings of MG and tested
2 by RT-PCR using universal (RSP48/RSP49) [9] and group-specific primers (IF/IR; IIF/IIR;
3 IIIF/IIIR) [10], designed for detection of extant molecular variants in the CP gene. RT-PCR
4 assays on GRSPaV-MG RNA extracts repeatedly confirmed infection with a single virus
5 variant referable to group I, which is thought to be closely associated with VN disease [11 ,
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12 The complete genome sequence was obtained using a stepwise RT-PCR-based
13 strategy (Fig. 1). Double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) was isolated from cortical scrapings of
14 dormant canes as previously described [13, 14]. Resulting dsRNA was denatured with 20
15 mM methylmercury hydroxide (CH₃HgOH) and reverse-transcribed using random hexamers
16 (Roche Diagnostics, USA) with M-MLV reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen, USA). First strand
17 cDNA synthesized was amplified with DreamTaq polymerase (Fermentas, Canada) using
18 PCR primers initially designed from sequences of GRSPaV isolates already available in
19 GenBank, and located in different genomic regions (Fig.1). PCR products were subsequently
20 cloned into the pSC-A vector (StrataClone PCR cloning kit, Agilent Technologies, USA) and
21 residual gaps were bridged using specific primers designed on previously sequenced
22 fragments. The 3' terminal region was amplified using the RSP52-specific primer [10] and an
23 oligo(dT)₃₂ primer that matched the reverse-transcribed poly(A) tail of the viral RNA. To
24 obtain the 5' end, the 5'/3' RACE Kit system was used (Roche Diagnostics, USA) with
25 nested reverse primers located 233 and 128 nts downstream the known 5' terminus,
26 respectively. All selected plasmids were extracted by boiling and PEG/NaCl purification and
27 custom sequenced (PRIMM, Italy). The resulting fragments were analysed and assembled
28 into a continuous sequence with the BioEdit 7.0.9 program (Ibis Biosciences, USA). Multiple
29 alignments with published sequences and percentage of nt identity and amino acid-derived
30 products were calculated using the Clustal X algorithm, version 2.0 [15]. Open reading frames
31 (ORFs) were identified using the NCBI ORF Finder, and amino acid (aa) conserved domains
32 were identified within the NCBI Conserved Domain Database using CD-Search [16].
33 Transmembrane domains (TMD) prediction was done using the Hidden Markov Model
34 TMHMM 2.0 [17]. Nuclear localization signals (NLS) in the capsid protein were detected
35 with the WoLF PSORT protein localization predictor [18].
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Sequence properties

GRSPaV-MG genome consisted of 8,725 nts, excluding the 3' poly (A) tail, and had a nt composition of 27.64% A, 19.37% B, 23.77 % G, 29.21% U, with a GC content of 43.1%. Genomic arrangement was typical of the *Foveavirus* genus [19] and identical to that of previously sequenced GRSPaV isolates possessing a sixth putative ORF (Fig. 1). The 5' and 3' non-coding regions (NCR) were 60 and 139 nts long, respectively. The 5' RACE analysis showed that the 5'-terminal base is a guanine, thus excluding the presence of an extra cytosine residue, so far reported only for isolate GRSPaV-1 [7].

ORF 1 (nt position 61-6546), identified as the viral replicase gene, putatively encodes a polypeptide of 2,161 aa comprising five conserved domains, distinctive of several positive sense ssRNA virus groups. In the order: the methyltransferase (M, aa 43-355); a cysteine protease (O, aa 1074-1175) homologous to the ovarian tumour (OTU) gene of *Drosophila spp.*; a peptidase (P, aa 1180-1268) belonging to the C23 Merops family, thought to be involved in auto-proteolysis of viral polyprotein; a helicase (H, aa 1352-1505) belonging to the UvrD-helicase superfamily [20]; the RNA-dependent RNA-polymerase (R, aa 1773-2148). Near the C-terminus of the latter domain (aa 2003-2038) there was the core motif TG(x)₃T(x)₃NT(x)₂₂, present in RNA polymerases of *Flexiviridae*. The AlkB-like domain related to the 2-oxoglutarate- and Fe(II)-dependent oxygenase superfamily was not identified by NCBI CD-search, but it was detected in the replicase cistron of our isolate (aa 781-877) by comparative Clustal X alignment with the AlkB-like residues described by Bratlie and Drablos [21]. In particular, the typically conserved motifs HxD, a single H and R(x)₆R, were identified within this domain. Thus, GRSPaV-MG is another representative of the families *Flexiviridae* and *Closteroviridae* sharing this feature. The replicase domain showed a distinctive AHIF motif (aa positions 558-561) which is not found in other known GRSPaV genomes, but recalls the homologous AHxF residues detected in the comparable region of a member of the genus *Capillovirus*, Apple stem grooving virus (ASGV; accession number BAA98054) and from its strain causing Citrus tatter leaf (CTLV; accession number BAA03869).

ORF 2 (nt 6577-7242), ORF 3 (nt 7244-7597) and ORF 4 (nt 7518-7760) constitute the triple gene block (TGB), encoding the putative proteins TGBp1 (221 aa), TGBp2 (116 aa) and TGBp3 (80 aa). TGBp1 possesses the conserved domain (aa 24-220) of an UvrD-helicase

1 already detected in the replicase gene, thus it may have an RNA-helicase function. Within this
2 domain, the conserved sites GKS (aa 33-35), responsible for ATP binding [23] and DEY (aa
3 83-85), described as the catalytic site of ATPase [24], were recognized. TGBp2 contains the
4 conserved signature of plant virus movement proteins superfamily (MP, aa 3-106), believed to
5 enable, together with TGBp1 and TGBp3, the cell-to-cell movement of flexiviruses [25].
6 Sequence analysis performed with TMHMM 2.0 confirmed the existence of two putative
7 TMDs (aa 7-29 and aa 79-101) in TGBp2 and one in TGBp3 (aa 2-21) whose relationships
8 with the endoplasmic reticulum were experimentally ascertained by Rebelo *et al.* [26].
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10 ORF 5 (nt 7770-8549) encodes the capsid protein (259 aa), with a calculated
11 molecular mass of 28,185 Da. The central part of the CP gene (aa 147-187) contains the motif
12 RR/Qx...FDF, proposed to have a role in the formation of a salt bridge structure and typically
13 conserved in all filamentous viruses [27]. It also comprises several aa motifs characteristic of
14 CPs of GRSPaV and other *Foveavirus* species [27]: ARHCxDVGxSxxSTL (aa 108-122);
15 YAKxVWN (aa 153-159) and PPANW (aa 167-171). Analysis with the WoLF PSORT
16 predictor allowed the detection of the nuclear localization signal KRKR near the N-terminus
17 (aa 47-50), which is responsible for the active nuclear targeting of GRSPaV CP, as
18 experimentally shown by Meng *et al.* [28].
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20 ORF 6 (nt 8227-8586) overlaps ORF 5 and encodes a hypothetical 13,884 Da protein
21 (119 aa). The presence of an additional 3'-most ORF, superimposed to the CP gene had
22 already been detected in strains GRSPaV, GRSPaV-1, GRSPaV-SG1, and GRSPaV-SY, but
23 not in GRSPaV-BS and GRSPaV-PN. Although it occurs also in the foveavirus Apricot latent
24 virus (ApLV) and two related variants [29], the existence in GRSPaV of a protein encoded by
25 ORF 6 has been questioned [30]. Notwithstanding the fact that GRSPaV-MG ORF 6
26 resembled in size and genomic position the RNA-binding proteins encoded by members of
27 **five genera in the family Flexiviridae** [25], a comparative database analysis did not reveal
28 significant matching nor conserved residues. By contrast, BLAST P analysis disclosed in aa
29 positions 62-112 a 32% identity with the expression product of ORF2 of the vitivirus
30 Grapevine virus B (GVB), which codes for an *in planta* expressed putative protein with
31 unknown function [31].
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33 Comparative analysis among GRSPaV-MG and other GRSPaV genomes, showed a
34 close relationship with strain GRSPaV-SG1. These isolates shared the highest overall
35 sequence identity value at the nucleotide level (93.7%), whereas the identity with other
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1 isolates ranged between 77.1% and 87.4%. The deduced aa sequence identities substantially
2 confirmed this situation, for their values were comprised between 85.8 and 95.3% .
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4 The close correlation of GRSPaV-MG with strain GRSPaV-SG1 was substantiated
5 when a detailed comparison of single ORFs was done. The replicase gene proved to be the
6 least conserved, as remarked earlier [22], showing the highest variation between the two
7 genomes, i.e. identity values of 93.5% and 95% at the nucleotide and amino acid levels,
8 respectively. In agreement with previous reports [19, 30], the CP gene was the most
9 conserved, for the two isolates shared identities of 96.1% at the nucleotide and 96.9% at the
10 amino acid level, the most relevant differentiation occurring in the N-terminal half of the
11 deduced protein (aa 1-130). In addition, it is worth pointing out that isolates GRSPaV-MG
12 and GRSPaV-SG1 have a similar biological behaviour, for neither of them induces pitting in
13 *V. rupestris*, but both cause VN in 110R, as ascertained by indexing of a GRSPaV-SG1
14 source available in our Department collection in both indicators (M. Morelli, unpublished
15 information).
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18 The description of this novel full-length genome sequence may help disclosing
19 pathogenic determinants in this group of GRSPaV molecular variants, whose close
20 association with VN has been experimentally ascertained (12).
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17 **Figure captions**
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21 **Fig. 1.** Schematic representation of the RNA genome of isolate GRSPaV-MG. Boxes
22 represent ORFs, with indication of the encoded putative proteins and conserved domains
23 identified using CD-Search on NCBI. Molecular weights are expressed in Da.
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26 **M**, Viral Methyltransferase domain; **A**, AlkB-like domain; **O**, OTU-like cysteine protease
27 domain; **P**, C23 peptidase domain; **H**, UvrD-helicase domain; **R**, RNA-dependent RNA
28 polymerase domain; **TGB**, Triple gene block; **CP**, capsid protein. The lines below the graph
29 represent the overlapping clones used to assemble the genome sequence, with primers used
30 for PCR amplification.
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